

ХОТИРА КУНИ МИЛЛИЙ МЕРОСНИ ЭСЛАТАДИ

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Annotasiya: Maqolada ikkinchi jahon urushi yillarida faol qatnashgan, yurt tinchligi uchun jonini fido etgan ajdodlarni xotirlash muqaddas burch ekanligi, 9-may –xotira kuni sifatida nishonlanishi, o‘tmishni yod etish milliy o‘zlikni anglatishi kabi masalalarga to‘xtab o‘tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Urush, xotira, meros, ajdodlar, Vatan.

Аннотация: В статье акцентируются такие вопросы, как то, что священным долгом является помнить о предках, активно участвовавших в годы Второй мировой войны, отдавших свою жизнь за мир в стране, что 9 мая отмечается как день памяти, и что память о прошлом означает национальную идентичность.

Ключевые слова: Война, память, наследие, предки, Родина.

Abstract: The article emphasizes such issues as the fact that it is a sacred duty to remember the ancestors who actively participated during the Second World War, who gave their lives for peace in the country, that May 9 is celebrated as a day of remembrance, and that memory of the past means national identity.

Key words: War, memory, heritage, ancestors, Motherland.

Inson, millat va xalq tarixiy xotira bilan barhayot. Xotira — kechagi o‘tmishni, ajdodlar o‘gitini, milliy merosimizni anglatib turuvchi — muqaddas kitob zarvaraqlaridek hayotimizni yoritib turadi. SHu bois, fashizmga qarshi kurashda halok bo‘lgan vatandoshlarimizning so‘nmas xotiralarini yod etib,

ularning xotirasi oldida hurmat bajo keltirish xalqimizga xos azaliy qadriyat bo'lib kelmoqda.

9 may – “Xotira va qadrlash kuni” mamlakatimizda umumxalq bayrami sifatida keng nishonlanadi. Inson xotira bilan tirik, qadr bilan ulug'. O'tganlarni, ularning xayrli ishlarini, jasoratini yodga olmoq, e'zozlamoq xalqimizga xos ezgu fazilatlardandir. Binobarin, xotira bu – unutmazlik, deganidir. Sohibqiron Amir Temur ham so'zini “Bizkim...” deya o'z Vatanini, xalqini, ajdodlarimiz hurmatini bajo etish bilan boshlagan. O'z navbatida, Mirzo Ulug'bek ham, shoir va sarkarda Bobur ham, shoirlar sultoni Alisher Navoiy ham ajdodlar ruhiga munosib, buyuk ishlarning davomchisi bo'lishga intilganlar. SHuning bilan birga, xotira – tiriklik chashmasidir. Undan imon-e'tiqod bilan suv ichganlar avlodi qudratli va salohiyatli bo'ladi.

Ikkinchi jahon urushida halok bo'lgan minglab yurtdoshlarimiz xotirasini yod etish, olovli janglardan omon qaytgan bobolarimizga, og'ir kunlarni sabr-bardosh bilan yenggan, mashaqqatli daqiqalarda ham o'zligini yo'qotmagan, imoni butun yurtdoshlarimizga hurmat-ehtirom ko'rsatish tom ma'noda milliy qadriyatga aylandi. O'tganlarni, ularning xayrli ishlarini, jasoratini yodga olmoq, e'zozlamoq xalqimizga xos ezgu fazilatlardan, qolaversa, bu bugun tom ma'noda milliy qadriyatga aylandi.

Xalqimizga xos bo'lgan mehr-oqibat, muruvvat va himmat barcha bayramlarimiz singari “Xotira va qadrlash kuni” misolida ham yorqin namoyon bo'ladi. Ayniqsa, o'tganlarni xotirlash, aziz otaxon-u onaxonlarning duosini olmoqlik saodati o'zgacha. Xotira shunday ruhiy-ma'naviy qudratki, u insonning insonligini anglatuvchi, uni o'tmish va istiqbol bilan bog'lab turuvchi buyuk qadriyat, ilohiy qudratdir. Xotirlash – xalq manfaati uchun kurashgan, el-yurt hurmatiga sazovor bo'lgan kishilarni eslashdir. U olamdan o'tgan ajdodlarni eslashgina emas, asrlar mobaynida Vatan uchun kurashda halok bo'lganlar xotirasini hurmatlash hamdir.

9 may – “Xotira va qadrlash kuni” munosabati bilan xalqimizning ezgu fazilatlari yanada yorqin namoyon bo'ladi. Ikkinchi jahon urushi dahshatlarini boshdan kechirgan kishilar osoyishtalikni dildan his qilgan, uning naqadar muhim ekanini anglab yetib, bu yo'lda Vatanini, oilasini, o'zligini himoya qilish uchun ikkilanmasdan jonini garovga qo'yib xizmat qilganlar. Ming afsuski, hozirgi kunda ularning saflari tobora kamayib bormoqda. YOshligining navqiron chog'larini urush olovlarida, janggohlarda o'tkazib, bugungi tinch va osoyishta hayotimiz uchun kurashgan insonlar jasorati beqiyosdir.

SHu o'rinda Ikkinchi jahon urushida halok bo'lgan minglab yurtdoshlarimiz xotirasini yod etish, olovli janggohlardan omon qaytgan bobolarimizga, og'ir kunlarni sabr-bardosh bilan yenggan, mashaqqatli daqiqalarda ham o'zligini yo'qotmagan, yurtdoshlarimizga hurmat-ehtirom ko'rsatish tom ma'noda milliy qadriyatga aylandi. Bu hol yoshlarni yurtparvarlik, mehnatsevarlik, ajdodlarining eng yaxshi an'analaridan faxrlanish, ularga munosib vorislar bo'lish ruhida tarbiyalashda beqiyos ahamiyatga ega. Xotirani asrash, xotirani ehtiyot qilish – bu bizning o'zimiz va avlodlar oldidagi axloqiy burchimizdir. Xotira – bizning boyligimizdir. Kechagi kun saboqlarini, xalqimiz kelajagi yo'lida jon fido qilgan insonlarni xotirlash bugungi kunimizni qadrlashga o'rgatadi. Xotira bu – tarix. U kechagi o'tmishni, ajdodlar o'gitini, milliy merosimizni anglatib turuvchi – muqaddas kitob zarvaraqlaridek hayotimizni yoritib turadi. SHu bois, inson o'z xotira boyligini qadrlaydi.

Inson bor ekan, xotira muqaddas. Ikkinchi jahon urushi haqiqatan ham insoniyat tarixidagi eng dahshatli, eng qonli qirg'in bo'lgan edi. Bu urush xalqimiz boshiga qanday og'ir azob-uqubat va talofatlar, behisob qurbonlar keltirganini el-yurtimiz hech qachon unutmaydi.

Sababi bu beshafqat urushda qatnashgan 2 millionga yaqin o'zbekistonliklarning yarim milliondan ziyodi halok bo'lgan. Bu yovuz urush tufayli qancha-qancha oilalar o'z boquvchisidan ajraldi, go'daklar yetim, ayollar

beva bo'lib qoldi. SHuningdek, yurtdoshlarimiz janglar davom etayotgan hududlardan O'zbekistonga ko'chirilgan 1,5 milliondan ortiq keksalar, ayollar va yosh go'daklarni bag'riga olib, og'ir damlarda ularga beqiyos g'amxo'rlik ko'rsatdi.

Xalq yaxshi farzandlarini hech qachon esdan chiqarmaydi. Xalqning xotirasiz yashashi aslo mumkin emas. Bu har qanday kishini ma'nan rag'batlantiradi, uni yashashga, elu-yurtga sadoqat va qat'iyat bilan xizmat qilishga undaydi.

SHu jihatdan, keksa avlod vakillariga e'tibor va g'amxo'rlikni kuchaytirish, ularning ijtimoiy ta'minoti, tibbiy xizmatdan foydalanishi, maishiy sharoitlarini yaxshilash, ularni e'zozlash va ardoqlash doim davlatimizning e'tibor markazida bo'lib qoladi, deb baralla ayta olaman. Zero, yillar o'tadi, zamonlar o'tadi, lekin Vatan ozodligi va erkinligi, el-yurtimizning tinch va osuda hayotini himoya qilishda kurashib jon bergan o'g'lonlar nomi va xotirasi xalqimiz yodida umrbod, abadiy saqlanib qoladi.

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